

Five strains of BB races 1, 2, and 3 were pin-prick inoculated into IR8 (race 1) and IR36 (races 2 and 3). Six doses each of the inoculum were used for each strain. The experiment was in a split-plot design with five replications. Host response was recorded on an all-or-none basis — healthy leaves or leaves with water-soaked BB lesions. Plant response records for each infection data were evaluated by probit analysis. The median effective dose (ED₅₀, the number of bacterial cells per plant that cause 50% of the inoculated rice leaves to respond, and the shape of the log dose/probit response curve were estimated by maximizing the likelihood function. The precision of estimates was determined using variance formulas. ED₅₀ values were based on the original number of cells in the inoculum at inoculation. Young, fully expanded leaves were observed at maximum tillering and flag leaves at booting.

Based on ED₅₀s, there were significant differences in virulence levels of different strains within the race group. However, virulence ranking was inconsistent with growth stage. Likewise, the range of bacterial cell numbers among the strains varied according to plant age. Among the strains, PXO 80 of race 1 and PXO 78 of race 2 were most virulent and differed significantly from the other strains of each race group at maximum tillering (Table 1, 2). There was no significant difference in virulence among race 3 strains (Table 3) except PXO 87 at flowering stage.

Tables 1, 2, and 3 showed the probit slopes resulting from the infectivity titrations of all isolates. The slopes were less than 2, indicating *X. c. pv. oryzae* cells probably act independently during growth *in vivo*, conforming to the hypothesis of independent action. Furthermore, the slope-probit regression also indicated that the host response could be heterogeneous in resistance, especially at booting, because slope values for each strain were much below 2. This may also be related to the nature of resistance of the varieties as they mature.

It seemed that varieties have more uniform susceptibilities at maximum tillering than at booting. Results also indicated

Table 2. Relationship of induction of positive infection^a and challenge doses of strains in virulence group II of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* on IR36 at 2 growth stages, IRRI.

Strain	Interaction (a)	Slope (b)	ED ₅₀ ^b	
			Cells ^c (no./ml)	95% fiducial limit
<i>Maximum tillering</i>				
PXO 63	-1.283629	1.193854	1.8 × 10 ⁵ c	1.4 × 10 ⁵ - 2.4 × 10 ⁵
PXO 78	0.778038	0.864323	7.7 × 10 ⁴ d	5.4 × 10 ⁴ - 1.1 × 10 ⁵
PXO 82	0.124390	0.913277	2.2 × 10 ⁵ bc	9.1 × 10 ⁴ - 4.9 × 10 ⁵
PXO 83	-0.844036	1.026089	4.9 × 10 ⁵ a	2.4 × 10 ⁵ - 1.0 × 10 ⁶
PXO 86	-0.290847	0.948272	3.8 × 10 ⁵ ab	2.7 × 10 ⁵ - 5.2 × 10 ⁵
<i>Flowering</i>				
PXO 63	-1.216944	1.091421	4.9 × 10 ⁵ ab	3.6 × 10 ⁵ - 6.8 × 10 ⁵
PXO 78	-1.018771	1.029397	7.0 × 10 ⁵ ab	5.2 × 10 ⁵ - 9.6 × 10 ⁵
PXO 82	-1.534185	1.169987	3.8 × 10 ⁵ b	1.3 × 10 ⁵ - 1.1 × 10 ⁶
PXO 83	-0.154857	0.922782	3.9 × 10 ⁵ b	7.1 × 10 ⁴ - 1.8 × 10 ⁶
PXO 86	0.216349	0.780476	1.3 × 10 ⁶ a	2.5 × 10 ⁵ - 5.7 × 10 ⁶

^a Scored at 14 d after inoculation. ^b Based on bacterial cell number in the inoculum suspension. ^c Separation of ED₅₀s at the same stage by Duncan's multiple range test at 5% level.

Table 3. Relationship of induction of positive infection^a and challenge doses of strains in virulence group III of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* on IR36 at 2 growth stages, IRRI.

Strain	Interaction (a)	Slope (b)	ED ₅₀ ^b	
			Cells ^c (no./ml)	95% fiducial limit
<i>Maximum tillering</i>				
PXO 22	-0.172836	0.852449	1.2 × 10 ⁶ a	2.5 × 10 ⁵ - 4.7 × 10 ⁶
PXO 79	1.113828	0.711859	2.9 × 10 ⁵ a	6.5 × 10 ⁴ - 1.0 × 10 ⁶
PXO 81	-0.288778	0.975468	2.6 × 10 ⁵ a	5.5 × 10 ⁴ - 1.1 × 10 ⁶
PXO 87	0.923749	0.690078	8.1 × 10 ⁵ a	1.6 × 10 ⁵ - 3.3 × 10 ⁶
PXO 88	1.491207	0.648439	2.6 × 10 ⁵ a	1.4 × 10 ⁴ - 1.4 × 10 ⁶
<i>Flowering</i>				
PXO 22	-0.841707	0.981978	8.9 × 10 ⁵ b	7.8 × 10 ⁴ - 6.2 × 10 ⁶
PXO 79	-1.379009	1.063169	9.9 × 10 ⁵ b	4.6 × 10 ⁵ - 2.0 × 10 ⁶
PXO 81	0.043882	0.867777	5.1 × 10 ⁵ b	-
PXO 87	-2.754767	1.110812	9.5 × 10 ⁶ a	7.2 × 10 ⁶ - 1.3 × 10 ⁷
PXO 88	-1.363441	1.092269	6.7 × 10 ⁵ b	3.2 × 10 ⁵ - 1.4 × 10 ⁶

^a Scored at 14 d after inoculation. ^b Based on bacterial cell number in the inoculum suspension. ^c Separation of ED₅₀s at the same stage by Duncan's multiple range test at 5% level.

that the dose-response probability function characterized by the ED₅₀ point may be useful to evaluate not only host resistance

but also virulence of a bacterial pathogen such as *X. c. pv. oryzae* on a self-pollinated host. □

Outbreak of rice tungro virus (RTV) in North Arcot District

P. Lakshmanan, T. Manoharan, and K. Ranganathan, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University Research Centre, Vellore 632001, Tamil Nadu, India

An RTV outbreak in North Arcot District, Tamil Nadu, in Feb-May 1984 resulted in severe infection of nearly 1,800 ha.

Locally grown rice varieties had markedly different infection severities. Disease incidence was recorded based on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

RTV infection in North Arcot, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Range of RTV infection (%)
IET1722	60-80
Co 37	60-80
TKM9	29-40
Co 43	15-20
IR20	15-20
IR50	0-12

IET1722 and Co 37 were highly susceptible to RTV, with 60-80% infection (see table). IR50 was RTV-resistant. □